

Relationship between Verbal Communication Apprehension and Achievement in Commerce of the Higher Secondary School Pupils of Thrissur District in Kerala State

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Abstract:- The present study is to find out the relationship between verbal communication apprehension and achievement in commerce of the higher secondary school pupils. **The Objectives:** 1. To find out whether there is any significant difference exists in the Mean scores of Verbal Communication Apprehension for the samples of Boys and Girls, Rural and Urban and Government and Private. 2. To find out whether there exists any relationship between Verbal Communication Apprehension and Achievement in Commerce of Higher secondary school pupils for total samples and comparable sub samples based on Sex, Locale and types of management. 3. To find out the effect of Verbal Communication Apprehension on Achievement in Commerce. **Methodology:** The researcher considered sample of this study consists of 496 students of standard XI selected from 9 Higher Secondary Schools of Thrissur District by stratified random sampling method. **Tool:** The tools used for the study are Verbal Communication Apprehension Scale and Achievement Test in Commerce which were modified by the researcher. **Findings:** The achievement in commerce have significantly influenced by locality of the school and type of management. But sex of the pupils has no significant effect on the achievements in commerce.

Keywords:- Communication Apprehension, Verbal Communication, Achievement in Commerce, Higher Secondary School Pupils.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is the acquisition of the art of the utilization of knowledge. Education is a powerful and fundamental force in the life of man. It plays an instrumental role in shaping the destiny of the individual and the future of mankind. Education, as a value generating force in society, rejuvenates the present civilization and lays the foundation for a further one. The world is becoming more competitive. The progress, welfare and security of the nation depend critically on a rapid planned and sustained growth in the quality and extent of education. Quality of performance has become the key factor for personal progress. Parents desire that their children climb the ladder of performance to high level as possible. This desire for a high level of achievement puts a lot of pressure on students, teachers, school administrators and in general the education system itself. In fact it appears as if the whole system of education reveals round the academic

achievement of students through various other outcomes are also expected from the system. In this competitive world, students are now being challenged to exhibit the ability to think, write, observe and speak effectively. Their communication problem is about right perception, use of information, analysis of situation, creation of impulses and findings ways to put across and handle messages.

II. NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Approximately 70% of our working day is spent in one or more types of communications. Talking to others, reading books and news papers, listening lectures, watching television – these activities link us to our environment, permit the development of higher mental processes and help to regulate all human behaviour. It may seem obvious to say that communication is important and it shapes the very quality of our lives. Higher secondary stage is the stage which brings the child in touch with world of work. It also provides the foundation for the real nation building. Commerce has now been recognized as an important subject and now one of the core subjects at the higher secondary stage. Achievement in commerce will be affected by several factors such as motivation, cognitive style, prior experience, personality characteristics, cognitive abilities, attitude towards academic work and communication skill. All education is communication, the reverse is also true, since as observed by the MacBride commission, "communication is not only a system of public information, but also an integral part of education and development and the practical application of education and communication policies frequently overlaps". In fact education and communication are two sides of the same coin.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A lot of research has been conducted on the relationship between communication apprehension and achievement in different subjects.

MrCrosky and Anderson (2002) conducted a study on the relationship between communication apprehension and academic achievement among college students. A series of studies are reported which indicate that high communication apprehensive have lower academic achievement in traditional interaction-oriented educational systems than low communication apprehensive. But that no similar

relationship exists in a communication resisted education system. Data are also reported indicating that high communication apprehensive prefer mass lecture classes over small classes while moderate and low communication apprehensive preferences are the reverse. The implications of these results for choosing or designing instructional systems are discussed.

Gardner, et. al., (2004) conducted a study on Oral and Written Communication apprehension in Accounting Students: Curriculum Impacts and Impacts on Academic Performance. The results from this New Zealand study show that students in their final year of study in which they are exposed to greater communication demands do not, on average, have higher levels of communication apprehension in earlier studies than their peers do. The levels of communication apprehension for final year students decline most markedly for those students starting with higher average levels of apprehension. The results fail to find any strong associations between levels of communication apprehension and students' abilities to advance in their studies or average levels of academic performance.

Wrench, et.al., (2006) conducted a study on Intercultural Communication: The Relationships Among Ethnocentrism, Intercultural Communication Apprehension, Religious Fundamentalism, Homonegativity, and Tolerance for Religious Disagreements. This study found a positive relationship between religious fundamentalism with ethnocentrism and homonegativity. The study further found a negative between tolerance for religious disagreement with ethnocentrism and religious fundamentalism.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study has the following objectives:

- To find out whether there is any significant difference exists in the Mean scores of Verbal Communication Apprehension for the samples of Boys and Girls, Rural and Urban and Government and Private.
- To find out whether there exists any relationship between Verbal Communication Apprehension and Achievement in Commerce of Higher secondary school pupils for total samples and comparable sub samples based on Sex, Locale and types if management
- To find out the effect of Verbal Communication Apprehension on Achievement in Commerce

V. HYPOTHESIS

The hypothesis of the study based on the major objective were formulated as follows:

- There will be significant difference in the mean source of verbal Communication Apprehension for the samples of boys and girls, Rural and Urban and Government and Private
- There will be significant relationship between Verbal Communication Apprehension and Achievement in Commerce in the total sample and sub samples based on Sex, Locale, and types of management
- The effect of Verbal Communication Apprehension on Achievement in Commerce will be significant

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The present study is intended to find out the relationship between the Verbal Communication Apprehension and Achievement in Commerce of Higher Secondary School Pupils. For this purpose, the investigator prepared one tool Verbal Communication Apprehension Scale and adopted another tool - Achievement test prepared by Aruna and Menon in order to find out the achievement of the pupils.

VII. METHODOLOGY

A. Sample

Sampling is necessary here because studying the whole population in order to arrive at generalization would be impractical. The sample of this study consists of 496 students of standard XI selected from 9 Higher Secondary Schools of Thrissur District by stratified random sampling method.

B. Tools Used

The tools used for the study are: 1. Verbal Communication Apprehension Scale (Aruna and Rasheed, 2007) and 2. Achievement Test in Commerce (Aruna, Menon and Menon, 2005)

C. Statistical Techniques Used

The following statistical techniques have been used for the analysis of data in the present study.

- Test of Significance of difference between means of large independent sample.
- Pearson's Product moment co-efficient of correlation.
- Test of significance of correlation coefficient.
- Verbal description of correlation co-efficient.
- Test of significance of the correlation by Fishers 't' test.
- The 0.99 confidence interval of 'r'
- Percentage variance
- One-way ANOVA

VIII. TENABILITY OF THE HYPOTHESES

A. Hypothesis – 1

The First hypotheses states that "There will be significant difference in the mean scores of Verbal Communication Apprehension for the samples of Boys, Girls, Rural and Urban and Government and Private".

Table 1: Hypothesis – 1

SI No.	Nature of Sample	Sub Samples	Number of Samples	Mean	Standard Division	Critical Ratio
1	LOCALE	Rural	N ₁	M ₁	SD ₁	1.155
			299	112.91	12.923	
		Urban	N ₂	M ₂	SD ₂	
			197	111.61	11.8	
2	SEX	Boys	N ₁	M ₁	SD ₁	3.738
			202	109.86	12.94	
		Girls	N ₂	M ₂	SD ₂	
			294	114.14	11.89	
3	TYPE OF MANAGEMENT	Govt	N ₁	M ₁	SD ₁	1.043
			198	113.11	11.97	
		Private	N ₂	M ₂	SD ₂	
			298	11.93	12.83	

The critical ratio obtained when the mean score of verbal communication apprehension compared with the groups of rural and urban, boys and girls, government and private were 1.155, 3.738, 1.043 respectively. It was found that significant difference exist I the mean scores of boys and girls. But in the sample of rural and urban, government and private there is no significant difference.

B. Hypothesis – 2

The Second hypotheses states that "There will be significant relationship between Verbal Communication Apprehension and Achievement in Commerce in the total and sub samples".

Table 2: Hypothesis - 2

SI No:	Nature of Samples	N	Coefficient of Correlation ‘r’
1	Total	496	0.0427
2	Rural	202	0.0072
3	Urban	294	0.1335
4	Boys	299	0.0405
5	Girls	197	0.0535
6	Govt	198	0.0881
7	Private	298	0.0301

On the interpretation of coefficient of correlation by considering its magnitude for the samples have negligible relationship. The relationship between verbal communication apprehension and achievement in commerce is positive and negligible. So the hypotheses is rejected.

C. Hypothesis – 3

The Third hypotheses states that "Investigation Of Effect Of Independent Variable Verbal Communication Apprehension On Achievement In Commerce".

Table 3: Hypothesis - 3

Source of Variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square of variation	F - Value	Level of significance
Between groups	37.331	2	18.666	.667	N.S
Within groups	13803.505	493			
Total	13840.836	495	27.999		

The result indicates that the ‘F’ value is 0.667 which is less than the table value for corresponding degrees of freedom at 0.01 level. The table value for corresponding degree of freedom at 0.01 level is 4.62. This implies that Achievement in commerce is not influenced by verbal communication apprehension for the total sample.

IX. IMPORTANT FINDINGS

- The achievement in commerce have significantly influenced by locality of the school and type of management. But sex of the pupils has no significant effect on the achievements in commerce.
- The verbal communication apprehension have significantly influenced by sex of the pupils.
- The relationship between verbal communication apprehension and achievement in commerce is positive and negligible.

- There is no significant difference exists in the mean scores of achievement in commerce between groups of Moderate Verbal Communication Apprehension and Low Verbal Communication Apprehension for the whole samples except the Urban sample

X. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION

- Students should not be punished for communicating in classroom. Teachers should be identified the communication apprehension and helped to overcome.
- Let students choose their seats in a classroom so that those with high levels of communication apprehension could sit there they feel safe.
- Create a warm and supporting classroom climate, where students feel free to speak out and where they are allowed to make mistakes.
- In teacher training, particular attention should be paid to developing the communication skills of teachers. So that they can serve as role models for students.

XI. CONCLUSION

The study reveals that the Communication Apprehension is a phenomenon that definitely influences the quality of life of people and in schools. We should try to prevent and / or surmount this behaviour and provide ample opportunities inside and outside the classroom to improve the communication skills.

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